

Comparative Study of the Eutectic Bodied Oil with Stand Oil

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Manuscript received 30 August, 1975, accepted 15 April 1977.

The eutectic bodied oil was compared with thermally bodied oil like stand oil. The methyl esters of the stand oil were separated into different fractions by distillation, urea-adductation and by column chromatography. All the fractions were analyzed by physical and chemical methods and by IR & NMR spectroscopies. Unlike the eutectic bodied oils, stand oil is free from any aromatic or other compounds. The diallylic protons appear to be most reactive in all the cases, however, these protons are more reactive in the preparation of eutectic bodied oils. In case of stand oil, Diels-Alder reaction is more prominent.

In the previous papers^{1,2} attempts were made to find out the composition of the oils bodied by eutectic saltmixtures. To compare the eutectic bodied oils, with thermally bodied oils, stand oils were also analyzed. The thermal dimerization product of methyl-*trans*-10-*trans*-12-octadecadienoate obtained by heating at 250° was investigated³. The dimer structure was shown to be a Diels-Alder reaction product. Polymerization by Diels-Alder reaction takes place in two different ways namely, (1) intermolecularly, (2) intra-molecularly. Besides the occurrence of these inter- and intra-molecular reactions during polymerization, there is cyclization of single fatty acid molecule containing two or more double bonds with the consequence that cyclohexene rings are formed. The excessive loss of unsaturation without consequent rise in viscosity has been attributed to cyclization changes in fatty acids. It has also been suggested that the initial sharp decrease in iodine value while cooking oils to produce stand oil is likely to be due to the cyclization of dienoic and trienoic acid radicals present in the oil, in the early stages of production⁴.

Now it is to be decided whether Diels-Alder reaction is the main or sole reaction of polymerization. To answer this point the dimers were produced by heat treatment of a variety of materials such as methyl-L-oleostearate, methyl linoleate, methyl linolenate and sunflower oil. By suitably directed degradations of these dimers it was established that six membered rings were in fact present. The dimers were brominated and oxidized by potassium permanganate to convert the substituted cyclohexenes to tetracarboxylic acids. The yield of the tetracarboxylic acids was of a few percentage which makes it doubtful that it is the sole reaction in oil polymerization. It may be possible that other type of reaction is taking place. This probability has recently received strong support from kinetic studies on the polymerization of methyl 9, 12-linoleate⁵.

These studies showed that a prior isomerization occurs, but it was shown that at least 86% of the dimer was formed by reaction mechanism not involving conjugated molecules. The initial stages in the direct

dimerization reaction is postulated on kinetic evidence to be a disproportionation reaction or in other words a hydrogen atom presumably from the 11-methylene group in one molecule is transferred to another molecule resulting in the formation of two free radicals. If the lone electron form in one radical pairs with the lone electron of the other, a dimer with C-C linkage will be formed⁶.

Intermolecular addition polymerization is not the only reaction through which glyceride can dimerize. Glyceride dimers may also be formed through interesterification reaction between glyceride monomers that contain dimeric fatty acid group as a result of intermolecular addition. It is shown that a considerable part of the overall molecular weight increases are due to this interesterification mechanism.

The most desirable configuration about the unsaturated linkages during the diene reaction is the *trans*, *trans* conjugated configuration. The *cis*, *trans* form is less suitable and *cis*, *cis* form is unsuitable. These facts can be reasonably deduced from the inspection of Fischer-Hirschfelder-Taylor models of such molecules which made it apparent that in the first case there is no interference to rotation around the central bond, whereas in the last case there is considerable steric hindrance⁶.

Experimental

The method of preparation of eutectic bodied oils and the apparatus used in the preparation are described in the previous paper (1). The methods of analyses and experimental techniques are also described in the previous papers^{1,2}. Three different samples of stand oil from linseed oil having different viscosities were prepared by heating at 300° under nitrogen atmosphere as shown in Table 1. The stand oils were fractionated in two different fractions, namely acetone-soluble and insoluble fractions using 2 volumes of dry acetone at 25°. The methyl esters of the stand oils, the acetone soluble and insoluble fractions were prepared by

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TABLE 1—PREPARATION OF STAND OILS & EUTECTIC BODIED OILS.

Sample No.	Type of Bodied Oil	Viscosity (Stokes)
18	Stand	1.21
19	Stand	4-4.36
20	Stand	17.56
21	Eutectic	1.21
22	Eutectic	4-4.36

TABLE 2—INFRA-RED DATA OF METHYL ESTERS OF ORIGINAL LINSEED OIL AND STAND OIL FRACTIONS.

Frequency (Cm ⁻¹)	Assignment	Linseed Oil	18 S	18 I
3410-3510	-OOH/-OH			
3010	<i>cis</i> -CH=CH			
2920	C-H Stretching			
2850				
1740	C=O Stretching of Ester			
1550	Phenyl nucleus	a	a	
965	Isolated trans	a	a	
19 S	20	21	22 S	22 I
	Dist Res	Dist Res	Dist Res	Dist Res
			tr	tr
	a	a	a	a

Dist=Distillate, Res=Residue, tr=trace, a=absent, Blank spaces indicate present.

analyzed in Varian A60A Model NMR spectrophotometer and the summary of the results are given in Table 3. The methyl esters of the stand oils were fractionated in two fractions, namely, urea-adductable and-nonadductable fractions. These fractions were also analyzed by NMR and the summary of the results are shown in Table 4. The methyl esters of bodied oils were also separated by column chromatographic technique into three fractions, namely, monomer, dimer and polymer. The monomer and dimer fractions were analyzed by NMR and the summary of the results are shown in Table 5. It was not possible to analyze the polymer fractions due to paucity of the samples.

Discussions

The results show that oxygenated groups like -OH/-OOH are present only in residue fractions of acetone-soluble and insoluble fractions (Table 2). All the fractions, however, are enriched with *trans* isomers. Table 3 shows that the formation of cyclohexene protons is higher in the stand oil than the eutectic bodied oils. Table 3 shows the analyses of eutectic bodied oils and stand oils. The olefinic protons have been decreased to 2.1 in the residue from insoluble fractions of sample 22, which is called 22 I (res). Unlike the eutectic bodied oils all the fractions of stand oils are free from any aromatic compounds. The decrease in diallylic protons is remarkable in all the cases. In sample 20, the diallylic protons have been decreased to 1.9 (3.0 in the original) while the olefinic protons have been decreased to only 3.8. In case of the eutectic bodied oils, the diallylic protons have been decreased to 1.5. The number of olefinic protons in 22S is very slightly higher than that of 22I indicating thereby that unsaturated double bonds are not the

TABLE 3—NUMBER OF PROTONS OF THE METHYL ESTERS OF ORIGINAL LINSEED, STAND OILS & EUTECTIC BODIED OILS.

Chemical Shift	Linseed Oil	18	18 S	18 I	19 S	19 I	20	22 S	22 I	22 S (Dist)	22 I (Res)
2.7	0.0	tr	0.0	tr	tr	tr	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
4.4	0.0	tr	tr	0.2	tr	0.3	0.0	0.0	tr	0.0	tr
4.6f	4.0	3.0	3.2	2.6	3.2	2.3	3.8	2.5	3.4	2.6	2.1
6.3	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
7.19	3.0	2.2	2.8	1.9	2.3	1.5	1.9	0.75	0.7	1.1	0.5
7.9f	6.0	5.4	5.5	5.1	5.2	5.0	6.4	6.2	6.2	6.7	6.6

tr = trace

transesterification using sodium methoxide as catalyst and were distilled at a pressure of 20μ and two fractions, namely, distillate and residue were collected. The original oil and the different fractions of the bodied oils were analyzed in infra-red spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer, Model 441). The summary of the infra-red analyses was given in Table 2. The original oil and the different fractions of the bodied oils were

major reacting centers. The diallylic protons have been decreased to 0.5 in 22 I (res) while olefinic protons have been decreased to 2.1 indicating thereby their greater reactivities.

Table 4 shows the proton numbers of the urea-fractions of the methyl esters of stand oils unlike the

TABLE 4—PROTON NUMBERS OF THE UREA FRACTIONS OF THE METHYL ESTERS OF STAND OILS AND EUTECTIC BODIED OILS.

Chemical Shift τ	Linseed Oil	18		19		20		21	
		UA	UR	UA	UR	UA	UR	UA	UR
2.7	0.0	0.0	tr	0.0	tr	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
4.4	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.9	0.0	1.1
4.62	4.0	2.0	2.6	2.1	2.8	2.8	3.7	2.3	2.3
6.3	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
6.59	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
7.19	3.0	1.9	1.4	3.0	1.3	1.9	1.5	1.5	1.2
7.91	6.0	6.1	5.4	6.0	5.3	6.4	5.5	6.0	5.1
8.8	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
9.2									

22	
UA	UR
0.0	0.0
0.0	1.6
1.9	2.5
3.0	3.0
0.0	0.0
1.4	1.0
5.8	5.0
3.0	3.0

TABLE 5—NUMBERS OF THE FRACTION OF METHYL ESTERS OF STAND OILS & EUTECTIC BODIED OILS BY COLUMN CHROMATOGRAPHY

Chemical Shift	Linseed Oil	18			19			20		21		22	
		M	D	O	M	D	O	M	D	M	D	M	D
2.7	0.0	0.0	tr	tr	0.0	tr	tr	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
4.4	0.0	tr	0.6	tr	tr	0.5	tr	tr	2.1	tr	2.5	tr	3.5
4.6	4.0	3.1	4.2	1.8	3.2	4.1	1.7	3.3	3.8	2.8	3.1	2.1	2.6
6.3	3.0	3.0	6.0	3.0	3.0	6.0	3.0	3.0	6.0	3.0	6.0	3.0	6.0
7.19	3.0	2.0	1.8	tr	1.9	1.7	tr	2.1	1.6	1.9	1.8	1.5	2.2
7.91	6.0	6.0	10.1	4.7	6.2	9.8	4.3	6.2	11.1	16.1	11.0	6.0	10.8
8.8													
to													
9.2	3.0	3.0	6.0	3.0	3.0	6.0	3.0	3.0	6.0	3.0	6.0	3.0	6.0

eutectic bodied oils, all the fractions are free from any aromatic or ether compounds. Like the eutectic bodied oils, all the fractions are free from any cyclohexene ring. The amount of cyclohexene ring increases in time of contact. The cyclohexene proton has been increased to only 0.3 in the nonadduct fraction from eutectic bodied oils but it increased to 1.6 in the corresponding nonadduct fraction from the stand oil. The cyclohexene proton is absent in all the

adductable fractions. The diallylic protons have been decreased to 1.6 and 1.2 in the adduct and nonadduct fractions respectively both from stand oil and eutectic bodied oils. The diminution of the α -methylene protons is not much in all the cases. So, it is evident that Diels-Alder reaction is much prominent in the thermal polymerization rather than the other process. In the eutectic bodied oils, more of polymerization has taken place through the diallylic protons*.

* The comparison is made between the stand oil and eutectic bodied oils which have similar viscosities.

Table 5 shows the proton numbers of the fractions of stand oil esters obtained by column chromatography. All the fractions are free from any aromatic or ether compounds. The amount of cyclohexene protons is much higher in the stand oil e.g. 2.5 in dimer from stand oil and 0.6 in dimer from eutectic bodied oils. The decrease in olefinic protons is also higher in stand oils, e.g. 3.1 in the dimer from the stand oil and 4.0 in the dimer from eutectic bodied oils. One remarkable feature is the large diminution in diallylic protons in the case of eutectic bodied oils, e.g., 1.8 in the monomer and 1.6 in the dimer. This indicates that diallylic protons are more reactive in presence of nitrate salts.

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